

On Visual Servoing under Field-of-View Limits and Impulsive Perturbations*

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Abstract—We consider the problem of image-based visual servoing (IBVS) under inelastic visibility constraints that arise from the field-of-view (FOV) of the camera. The target is affected by possible aperiodic impulse perturbations. Under the assumption that a minimum time needs to elapse after each impulse, the proposed controller guarantees that all image features will remain strictly inside the FOV and will converge to the desired feature values with prescribed performance characteristics, related to accuracy and convergence time, between any two consecutive impulses. Simulation results clarify and verify the theoretical findings.

I. INTRODUCTION

The inclusion of visual information in a control system is referred to as visual servoing and has attracted considerable attention over the past years. The visual servoing approaches are classified into three distinct categories: a) Image-Based Visual Servoing (IBVS); b) Position-Based Visual Servoing (PBVS); c) Hybrid Visual Servoing (HVS). In IBVS, the main objective is to derive the image features on the 2D image plane from their current to some desired position. On the contrary, in PBVS the visual information is used in conjunction with the shape of the target and the intrinsic parameters of the camera, to estimate the current 3D pose of the target relative to the camera. Compared to IBVS, methodologies that are classified as PBVS are computationally heavier and more sensitive to noise in the image plane and to calibration errors. The HVS approaches appeared to relax, to some extent, the computational burden of PBVS [1], [2]. Still, however, are sensitive to noise and calibration and computationally heavier compared to IBVS. These attributes motivate the use of IBVS methodologies for more high-speed tasks [3]–[7]. In this work, we will consider IBVS schemes.

A critical issue in IBVS is the satisfaction of the field-of-view (FOV) constraints. Indeed, task failure or even instability may be experienced, if some features escape the vision system FOV during the servo [8]. Owing to its significance, various approaches have been reported. These include path planning [9]–[13], model predictive control (MPC) [14]–[17] and task priority schemes [18], [19]. However, the aforementioned works do not guarantee the satisfaction of constraints and they are computationally demanding, making their implementation on control platforms with limited processing capabilities questionable.

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An additional highly significant issue within IBVS is achieving desirable transient and steady-state performance specifications on the response of the closed-loop system. The common practice to succeed in this task is via carefully tuning the control gains. However, in this way, the aforementioned performance attributes cannot be predetermined. Towards this end, the prescribed performance control (PPC) methodology [20]–[23] presents a valid approach. A kinematic PPC solution to the problem was provided in [24], despite the presence of calibration and depth measurement errors, while the inclusion of robust dynamics, which may even be uncertain, in the stability and performance analysis was succeeded in [25].

Nevertheless, none of the aforementioned works consider the possible appearance of impulsive behavior that may appear owing to accidental camera collisions with obstacles in the workspace and frame losses. Impulsive systems incorporate both continuous and discontinuous dynamics [26], making their stability analysis a challenging task. The presence of concurrent hard visibility constraints (i.e., FOV limits), elevate further the difficulty in succeeding this task. To the best of the authors' knowledge, no results have been reported thus far in the related literature.

In this work, we utilize the PPC methodology to propose a kinematic IBVS solution that achieves prescribed transient and steady-state performance attributes on the output tracking error, while respecting the inelastic FOV limits of the camera, despite the appearance of impulsive phenomena. More specifically, the impulses affecting the system can be aperiodic and their magnitude is unknown in advance. Nevertheless, a minimum time needs to elapse between any two consecutive impulses. The proposed controller guarantees that the position of the image feature will converge to a neighborhood of the desired position of preselected size, before a predefined, and user-selected, time has passed since the last impulse appearance. Additionally, all signals in the closed-loop remain bounded. Simulations clarify and verify the theoretical findings.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION AND PRELIMINARIES

Consider a 3D vision system following the pinhole camera model [27]. Let O_c be the center of the vision system, and the vision system frame $\{C\}$, with axes $[X_c Y_c Z_c]^T$, attached to it. The center of the image frame $\{I\}$ is represented with O_I as shown in figure 1, while $[\chi \psi]^T$ denote the coordinates of the image frame. Notice that the Z_c axis of the camera frame is perpendicular to the image plane traversing O_I .

Fig. 1. The geometric model of a pinhole camera.

Thus, given a set of fixed p 3D points $P_i = [x_i \ y_i \ z_i]^T$, $i = 1, \dots, p$ expressed in the camera frame, the image features $s_i = [\chi_i \ \psi_i]^T$, $i = 1, \dots, p$, are the corresponding projections into the 2D image plane and are given as [27]:

$$s_i = \begin{bmatrix} \chi_i \\ \psi_i \end{bmatrix} = \frac{f_c}{z_i} \begin{bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where f_c denotes the focal length of the vision system. To derive (1), it is assumed, without losing generality, that both the horizontal and vertical focal lengths coincide. In this way, the vision sensor velocity $V_s = [u_x \ u_y \ u_z \ \omega_x \ \omega_y \ \omega_z]^T$, where $u_j, \omega_j, j = \{x, y, z\}$ denote the translational and angular velocities in the vision sensor frame respectively, is related to the visual features' derivative as [1]:

$$\dot{s}_i = L_i(z_i, s_i)V_s, \quad i = 1, \dots, p, \quad (2)$$

where

$$L_i(z_i, s_i) = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{f_c}{z_i} & 0 & \frac{f_c x_i}{z_i} & \chi_i \psi_i & -(1+\chi_i^2) & \psi_i \\ 0 & -\frac{f_c}{z_i} & \frac{f_c y_i}{z_i} & (1+\psi_i^2) & -\chi_i \psi_i & -\chi_i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

is the interaction matrix. Define the overall visual feature vector as $s = [s_1^T \dots s_p^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2p}$. Then, (2) is written in compact form as

$$\dot{s} = L(z, s)V_s, \quad (4)$$

where $L(z, s) = [L_1^T(z_1, s_1) \dots L_p^T(z_p, s_p)]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2p \times 6}$ is the overall interaction matrix and $z = [z_1 \dots z_p]^T \in \mathbb{R}^p$ the overall depth vector. In (4), V_s constitute external inputs to the system. Furthermore, a significant issue of image based visual servoing is ensuring that all features coordinates do not violate the field of view limits. Owing to the aforementioned issue, the image plane coordinates are subject to the following visual (field-of-view) constraints:

$$\chi_m \leq \chi_i \leq \chi_M, \quad \psi_m \leq \psi_i \leq \psi_M, \quad i = 1, \dots, p. \quad (5)$$

where χ_m, χ_M and ψ_m, ψ_M are the lower and upper bounds of the corresponding image plane coordinates χ and ψ . Let χ_i^*, ψ_i^* be the desired features values for each point P_i respectively. We define the image feature errors as:

$$e_i^\chi(t) = \chi_i(t) - \chi_i^*, \quad e_i^\psi(t) = \psi_i(t) - \psi_i^*, \quad i = 1, \dots, p. \quad (6)$$

Let $e = [e_1^\chi, e_1^\psi, \dots, e_p^\chi, e_p^\psi]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2p}$, be the overall feature error vector. We consider the evolution of $s_i, i = 1, \dots, p$ to be affected by impulsive perturbations, which may appear owing to various factors e.g., accidental camera collisions with obstacles in the workspace, frame losses, etc. Therefore, the visual feature dynamics (2) become:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{s}_i(t) &= L_i(z_i(t), s_i(t))V_s(t), \quad i = 1, \dots, p, \quad t \notin \mathbb{J}, \\ s_i(t) &= s_i(t^-) + \Delta s_i(k), \quad i = 1, \dots, p, \quad t \in \mathbb{J}, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $\Delta s_i(k), k \in \mathbb{N}_+$ denotes the induced impulses in the system and $\mathbb{J} = \{t_k : k \in \mathbb{N}_+\}$, short for $\{t_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}_+}$,

represents the set of impulse sequence.

Assumption 1: For all $i = 1, \dots, p$, it holds that $\chi_m \leq \chi_i(t_0) \leq \chi_M, \psi_m \leq \psi_i(t_0) \leq \psi_M$.

Assumption 2: The impulse sequence satisfy $t_{k+1} - t_k \geq \bar{\tau} > 0, k \in \mathbb{N}_+$, where $\bar{\tau}$ is known. However, the exact impulse time instants are unknown.

Assumption 3: For all $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$, the impulses $\Delta s_i(k) = [\Delta \chi_i(k) \ \Delta \psi_i(k)]^T, i = 1, \dots, p$ are bounded and $\chi_m \leq \chi_i(t) \leq \chi_M, \psi_m \leq \psi_i(t) \leq \psi_M$, for all $t \in \mathbb{J}$.

Remark 1: Assumption 1 implies that the image features initially lie inside the vision sensor field of view. Assumption 2 imposes a lower bound of the time interval between two consecutive impulses. However, the exact time interval between any two consecutive impulses is unknown and therefore not available for the control design. Assumption 3 implies that the external phenomena that result in the appearance of impulsive perturbations on the visual features are not severe enough to force them to violate instantaneously the field-of-view constraints. A valid approach to handle, to some extent, such an unfortunate scenario could be via estimating the values of the lost features, by possibly exploiting the geometric characteristics of the target object which generate the points $P_i, i = 1, \dots, p$. Nevertheless, this is a very interesting problem whose solution is not trivial and it is left open for future investigations.

Control Objective: Consider the nonlinear impulsive system (7) satisfying Assumptions 1-3. Consider also the desired features values $\chi_i^*, \psi_i^*, i = 1, \dots, p$ and the corresponding image feature errors e_i^χ, e_i^ψ . Design a vision sensor velocity controller V_s to guarantee that a) the image feature errors will be strictly less than a prespecified value $\delta_i > 0$ for all $i = 1, \dots, p$, and $t \in [t_k + \tau, t_{k+1}), \tau < \bar{\tau}, k \in \mathbb{N}$ where $\tau > 0$ is a predefined fixed time; b) all signals in the closed loop are bounded; c) the field-of-view constraints (5) are preserved for all $t \geq t_0 \geq 0$.

III. MAIN RESULTS

The following theorem, whose proof is presented in Section IV, summarize the main results of this work.

Theorem 1: Consider the impulsive system (7), the FOV constraints (5) and Assumptions 1-3. Let τ be a prespecified time instant satisfying $\bar{\tau} > \tau > 0$ and $\delta_i > 0, i = 1, \dots, p$ are given constants. Define $\xi = [\xi_1^\chi \ \xi_1^\psi \ \dots \ \xi_p^\chi \ \xi_p^\psi]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2p}$, $\epsilon = [\epsilon_1^\chi \ \epsilon_1^\psi \ \dots \ \epsilon_p^\chi \ \epsilon_p^\psi]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2p}$, and $\alpha = [(\epsilon_1^\chi)^3 \ (\epsilon_1^\psi)^3 \ \dots \ (\epsilon_p^\chi)^3 \ (\epsilon_p^\psi)^3]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2p}$, where for all $i = 1, \dots, p, \sigma = \{\chi, \psi\}$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\xi_i^\sigma(t) = \frac{e_i^\sigma(t) - \frac{\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t) - \rho_i^\sigma(t)}{2}}{\frac{\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t) + \rho_i^\sigma(t)}{2}}, \quad \epsilon_i^\sigma(t) = \ln\left(\frac{1 + \xi_i^\sigma(t) \frac{\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t)}{\rho_i^\sigma(t)}}{1 - \xi_i^\sigma(t) \frac{\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t)}{\rho_i^\sigma(t)}}\right), \quad (8a)$$

$$\rho_i^\sigma(t) = \begin{cases} (\rho_{i,k}^\sigma - \rho_i^\infty) e^{-\lambda_{i,k}(t-t_k)} + \rho_i^\infty, & t \in [t_k, t_{k+1}) \\ \rho_i^\sigma(t^-) + \Delta \rho_i^\sigma(k), & t \in \mathbb{J} \end{cases}, \quad (8b)$$

$$\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t) = \begin{cases} (\bar{\rho}_{i,k}^\sigma - \rho_i^\infty) e^{-\lambda_{i,k}(t-t_k)} + \rho_i^\infty, & t \in [t_k, t_{k+1}) \\ \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t^-) + \Delta \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(k), & t \in \mathbb{J} \end{cases}, \quad (8c)$$

with $\Delta\rho_i^\sigma(k) = \beta_i|\Delta\sigma|_i(k)$, $\Delta\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(k) = \bar{\beta}_i|\Delta\sigma|_i(k)$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$, the constants $\beta_i, \bar{\beta}_i > 1$ and $\rho_{i,k}^\sigma, \bar{\rho}_{i,k}^\sigma \geq \rho_i^\infty > 0$, $\rho_i^\infty < \delta_i$, $-\rho_{i,0}^\sigma := -\rho_i^\sigma(t_0) < e_i^\sigma(t_0) < \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t_0) := \bar{\rho}_{i,0}^\sigma$. Finally

$$\lambda_{i,k} > \max \left\{ \ln \left(\frac{\rho_{i,k}^\chi - \rho_i^\infty}{\delta_i - \rho_i^\infty} \right) / \tau, \ln \left(\frac{\rho_{i,k}^\psi - \rho_i^\infty}{\delta_i - \rho_i^\infty} \right) / \tau, \right. \\ \left. \ln \left(\frac{\bar{\rho}_{i,k}^\chi - \rho_i^\infty}{\delta_i - \rho_i^\infty} \right) / \tau, \ln \left(\frac{\bar{\rho}_{i,k}^\psi - \rho_i^\infty}{\delta_i - \rho_i^\infty} \right) / \tau \right\}. \quad (8d)$$

Let $\Lambda = [\Lambda_{i,j}] \in \mathbb{R}^{2p \times 6}$ with $\Lambda_{i,j} = L_{i,j}^3$ and Λ^+, L^+ are the pseudo-inverse matrices of Λ and L respectively. The control law

$$V_s(t) = -k_s \Lambda^+ \alpha(\xi(t)) - k'_s L^+ \epsilon(\xi(t)) \in \mathbb{R}^6, \quad (8e)$$

with k_s, k'_s be some strictly positive design constants, guarantees: i) $|e_i^\sigma(t)| < \delta_i$, for all $t \in [t_k + \tau, t_{k+1})$; ii) the boundedness of all signals in the closed loop.

Remark 2: It may deceptively appear that controller (8) does not incorporate FOV constraints. However, the latter can be easily introduced by selecting:

$$\rho_{i,0}^\sigma = \underline{W}_i^\sigma, \bar{\rho}_{i,0}^\sigma = \overline{W}_i^\sigma, i = 1, \dots, p, \sigma = \{\chi, \psi\}, \quad (9)$$

where $\underline{W}_i^\chi := \chi_i^* - \chi_m$, $\underline{W}_i^\psi := \psi_i^* - \psi_m$, $\overline{W}_i^\chi := \chi_M - \chi_i^*$, $\overline{W}_i^\psi := \psi_M - \psi_i^*$, and modify $\rho_i^\sigma(t), \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t)$ at $t \in \mathbb{J}$ as follows:

$$\rho_i^\sigma(t) = \begin{cases} \rho_i^\sigma(t^-) + \Delta\rho_i^\sigma(k), & \rho_i^\sigma(t^-) + \Delta\rho_i^\sigma(k) < \underline{W}_i^\sigma \\ \underline{W}_i^\sigma, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (10a)$$

$$\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t) = \begin{cases} \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t^-) + \Delta\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(k), & \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t^-) + \Delta\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(k) < \overline{W}_i^\sigma \\ \overline{W}_i^\sigma, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (10b)$$

The rest of the controller equations remain unaltered.

Remark 3: The impulsive dynamics (8b)-(8c) and (10) define an event-like triggering mechanism. The discontinuities indicated by (8b)-(8c) and (10) and the calculation of the lower bound of $\lambda_{i,k}$ in (8d) take place simultaneously, as soon as an impulse appears at the time instant t_k , $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$. Hence, the time instants t_k are a priori unknown.

Remark 4: The visual servoing performance specifications are introduced via the performance functions $\rho_i^\sigma(t)$ and $\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t)$ for all $\sigma = \{\chi, \psi\}$ and $i = 1, \dots, p$. Specifically, given the initial conditions $s(t_0)$ and the performance parameters δ_i, τ , we select $\rho_i^\infty < \delta_i$ and the parameters $\rho_{i,k}^\sigma, \bar{\rho}_{i,k}^\sigma, \lambda_{i,k}$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$ according to (8d), (9) and (10). Hence, the construction of $\rho_i^\sigma(t), \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t)$ is completed. The aforementioned performance functions will enforce the specific performance requirements on the image feature errors stated in the control objective. The control gains $k_s, k'_s, \beta_i, \bar{\beta}_i$ can be freely chosen. Extensive simulations studies, however, have revealed that all these selections influence the overall performance. Specifically, large $\lambda_{i,k}$, small ρ_i^∞ and high-valued control gains k_s, k'_s result in significant or even prohibitively large control effort in the transient, while exhibiting satisfactory performance at steady-state. However, fine transient and oscillatory steady-state behavior will be

the case if the opposite selection is made. Furthermore, as it is clear from (10), high-value control gains $\beta_i, \bar{\beta}_i$ will practically reset the problem. By resetting the problem, we mean that the values of $\rho_i^\sigma(t), \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t)$, will regain their values obtained after each impulse appearance. Consequently, the design parameters, if carefully selected, may positively influence the quality of the image feature error evolution inside their corresponding performance envelopes, as well as of the produced control signal in terms of magnitude and slew-rate.

IV. PROOF OF THEOREM 1

Differentiating (8a) with respect to time, for $i = 1, \dots, p$ and $\sigma = \{\chi, \psi\}$, yields:

$$\dot{\xi}_i^\sigma = \frac{2\dot{e}_i^\sigma}{\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma + \rho_i^\sigma} - \frac{\dot{\bar{\rho}}_i^\sigma - \dot{\rho}_i^\sigma}{\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma + \rho_i^\sigma} - 2 \frac{\dot{\bar{\rho}}_i^\sigma + \dot{\rho}_i^\sigma}{(\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma + \rho_i^\sigma)^2} \left(e_i^\sigma - \frac{\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma - \rho_i^\sigma}{2} \right). \quad (11)$$

Hence, by definition of ξ in Theorem 1 the closed-loop system takes the form

$$\dot{\xi} = h(\xi, t) = [h_1, \dots, h_{2p}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2p}, \quad (12)$$

where the h -functions are the right-hand sides of (11).

Additionally, let us define the open set $\Omega_\xi = (-1, 1)^{2p} \subset \mathbb{R}^{2p}$. To prove Theorem 1, it is sufficient to show that controller (8), guarantees that e_i^σ remain bounded. Notice, that, by construction, e_i^σ is strictly increasing with respect of ξ_i^σ . Therefore, guaranteeing boundedness of e_i^σ , is equivalent to proving that ξ evolves strictly within a subset of Ω_ξ for all $t \geq t_0 \geq 0$. Thus, all closed-loop signals ξ_i^σ, V_s will remain bounded.

The proof of Theorem 1 consists of two lemmas. In Lemma 1, prescribe performance characteristics are enforced $\forall t \in [t_k, t_{k+1})$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, while in Lemma 2, the boundedness of all signals in the closed-loop is proved.

Lemma 1: Consider the visual servoing problem that obeys the nonlinear impulsive system (7) and Assumptions 1-3. Controller (8) guarantees that $|e_i^\sigma(t)| < \delta_i$, for $i = 1, \dots, p$, $\sigma = \{\chi, \psi\}$ and for all $t \in [t_k + \tau, t_{k+1})$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proof: The proof of this lemma consists of three phases. First, a unique maximal solution $\xi(t)$ of (12) over the set Ω_ξ is obtained for a time interval $[t_0, \tau_{max})$, with $t_0 = 0$ and $\tau_{max} \leq t_1$. Then, in the second phase, we extend the τ_{max} to t_1 . Finally, in the third phase the extension of the aforementioned results for all time intervals $[t_k, t_{k+1})$, $k \geq 1$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$ is accomplished.

Phase A: The set Ω_ξ is open and non-empty. Also, $\rho_i^\sigma(t_0)$ are selected such that $\xi(t_0) \in \Omega_\xi$. Moreover, it is clear from (11) that $h(\xi, t)$ in (12) is continuous on t and locally Lipschitz on ξ over Ω_ξ . Hence [28], there exists a unique maximal solution of $\xi(t)$ in $[t_0, \tau_{max})$, with $\tau_{max} \in [t_0, t_1]$.

Phase B: Owing to the results of Phase A, we conclude that $\xi_i^\sigma \in (-1, 1)$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Therefore, ϵ and α defined in Theorem 1, are initially well defined for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Furthermore, define $\zeta := L^+ \epsilon$, and differentiating it with respect to time, we obtain:

$$\dot{\zeta} = \frac{dL^+}{dt} \epsilon + L^+ \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial \xi} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial e} LV_s + \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} \right) + \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial t} \right). \quad (13)$$

Moreover, following the argumentation of [29], we obtain:

$$\frac{dL^+}{dt}\epsilon = O(e, t)V, \quad (14)$$

where $O \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$ satisfies $O(0, t) = 0$, for all $t \in [t_0, t_1]$. Denoting $Z = \Lambda^+\alpha$, we have $Z_j = \zeta_j^3$, $j = 1, \dots, 6$. Thus, substituting (14) and the control law (8e) into (13), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\zeta} = & - \left[O(e, t) + L^+ \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial e} \right) L \right] (k_s Z + k'_s \zeta) \\ & + L^+ \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial t} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Linearising (15) around $\zeta = 0$ or equivalently around $e = 0$, yields:

$$\dot{\zeta} = -A(t)(k_s Z + k'_s \zeta) + B(t), \quad (16)$$

where

$$A(t) = L^+ \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial e} \right) L \Big|_{e=0}, \quad B(t) = L^+ \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial t} \right) \Big|_{e=0}.$$

Define the positive definite function $V = \frac{1}{2} \zeta^T \zeta$ and differentiating V with respect to time and using (16) we obtain:

$$\dot{V} = -k_s \zeta^T A(t) Z - k'_s \zeta^T A(t) \zeta + \zeta^T B(t) \quad (17)$$

Notice that $\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial e}$ is a diagonal positive definite matrix by construction and therefore, following the argumentation of [30, Proposition 1], we conclude that $A(t)$ is also positive definite. Furthermore, utilizing the results of Phase A, it is obtain that $B(t)$ is bounded for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max}]$. Thus, we conclude the existence of a positive constant \bar{B}_0 such as $B(t) \leq \bar{B}_0$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max}]$. Moreover, utilizing $\zeta^T Z < \|\zeta\|^4/6$, \dot{V} becomes:

$$\dot{V} \leq -\frac{k_s \lambda_A \|\zeta\|^4}{6} + \frac{\bar{B}_0^2}{4k'_s \lambda_A} \quad (18)$$

where λ_A denotes the minimum eigenvalue of A . Therefore, $\dot{V} < 0$ when $\|\zeta\| \geq \sqrt[4]{6\bar{B}_0^2/4k'_s k_s \lambda_A^2}$. Thus, $\|\zeta(t)\| \leq \bar{\zeta} := \max \left\{ \|\zeta(t_0)\|, \sqrt[4]{6\bar{B}_0^2/4k'_s k_s \lambda_A^2} \right\}$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max}]$. Additionally, in the neighborhood of $\epsilon = 0$ (or equivalently of $e = 0$), it holds that $\|\zeta\| = \|L^+ \epsilon\| \neq 0$, if $\epsilon \neq 0$ (or equivalently if $e \neq 0$). Thus, there exists a positive constant Δ such that $\|\zeta\| = \|L^+ \epsilon\| \geq \Delta \|\epsilon\|$ and therefore $\|\epsilon\| \leq \bar{\zeta}/\Delta$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max}]$. Taking the inverse logarithmic function (8a) yields:

$$-1 < \underline{\xi}_i^\sigma \leq \xi_i^\sigma(t) \leq \bar{\xi}_i^\sigma < 1, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, \tau_{max}], \quad (19)$$

where

$$\underline{\xi}_i^\sigma = \frac{1 - \max \left\{ 1, \frac{\bar{W}_i^\sigma}{\bar{W}_i^\sigma} \right\} \exp\left(\frac{\bar{\zeta}}{\Delta}\right)}{1 + \max \left\{ 1, \frac{\bar{W}_i^\sigma}{\bar{W}_i^\sigma} \right\} \exp\left(\frac{\bar{\zeta}}{\Delta}\right)}, \quad (20a)$$

$$\bar{\xi}_i^\sigma = \frac{-1 + \max \left\{ 1, \frac{\bar{W}_i^\sigma}{\bar{W}_i^\sigma} \right\} \exp\left(\frac{\bar{\zeta}}{\Delta}\right)}{1 + \max \left\{ 1, \frac{\bar{W}_i^\sigma}{\bar{W}_i^\sigma} \right\} \exp\left(\frac{\bar{\zeta}}{\Delta}\right)}. \quad (20b)$$

Finally, from (19), we conclude that ξ evolves strictly within a compact subset of $\Omega'_{\xi_k} \subset \Omega_\xi$, where Ω'_{ξ_k} depends on \bar{B}_0 . Hence, the overall feature vector s and the control law V_s are bounded for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max}]$. At this point, using standard arguments [28], we extend τ_{max} to t_1 .

Phase C: In this phase, we will present that if $\xi(t_1^-) \in \Omega_\xi$

then $\xi(t_1) \in \Omega_\xi$ as well. Owing to $|\xi_i^\sigma(t_1^-)| < 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} -\underline{\rho}_i^\sigma(t_1^-) & < e_i^\sigma(t_1^-) < \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t_1^-), \quad \sigma = \{\chi, \psi\} \\ -\underline{\rho}_i^\sigma(t_1^-) & < [\sigma]_i(t_1^-) - [\sigma]_i^* < \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t_1^-). \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Firstly, we will examine the case that $\underline{\rho}_i^\sigma(t^-) + \beta_i |\Delta\sigma]_i(k)| < \underline{W}_i^\sigma$ and $\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t^-) + \bar{\beta}_i |\Delta\sigma]_i(k)| < \bar{W}_i^\sigma$. Using (8c), (8b), and (7), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} -\underline{\rho}_i^\sigma(t_1) + \beta_i |\Delta\sigma]_i(1)| & < [\sigma]_i(t_1) - [\Delta\sigma]_i(1) - [\sigma]_i^* \\ & < \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t_1) - \bar{\beta}_i |\Delta\sigma]_i(1)| \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\underline{\rho}_i^\sigma(t_1) + \beta_i |\Delta\sigma]_i(1)| + [\Delta\sigma]_i(1) & < [\sigma]_i(t_1) - [\sigma]_i^* \\ & < \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t_1) - \bar{\beta}_i |\Delta\sigma]_i(1)| + [\Delta\sigma]_i(1). \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

As $\beta_i, \bar{\beta}_i > 1$, we conclude that $\beta_i |\Delta\sigma]_i(1)| + [\Delta\sigma]_i(1) > 0$ and $-\bar{\beta}_i |\Delta\sigma]_i(1)| + [\Delta\sigma]_i(1) < 0$. Therefore, $-\underline{\rho}_i^\sigma(t_1) < e_i^\sigma(t_1) < \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t_1)$. In the case that both $\underline{\rho}_i^\sigma(t^-) + \beta_i |\Delta\sigma]_i(k)| > \underline{W}_i^\sigma$ and $\bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t^-) + \bar{\beta}_i |\Delta\sigma]_i(k)| > \bar{W}_i^\sigma$, then taking into consideration (10), we obtain $-\underline{\rho}_i^\sigma(t_1) = -\underline{W}_i^\sigma < e_i^\sigma(t_1) < \bar{W}_i^\sigma = \bar{\rho}_i^\sigma(t_1)$, which holds true owing to Assumption 3. The analysis of the rest of the possible cases follows trivially from the aforementioned statements and it is therefore omitted. Thus, proving $\xi(t_1) \in \Omega_\xi$. The line of proof of phases A, B, C is recursively repeated for all $[t_k, t_{k+1})$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$; thus proving Lemma 1.

Continuing from the last part of the proof of Lemma 1, we stress that the upper bound of $B(t)$, even though it exists, may vary with $k \in \mathbb{N}$, which consequently may enlarge the size of Ω'_{ξ_k} where $\xi(t)$ evolves, for all $t \in [t_k, t_{k+1})$. Therefore, the boundedness of all signals in the closed-loop remains, at this point, open. To conclude boundedness, we have to prove that $V(t_k)$ is upper bounded by a constant independent of $V(t_{k-1})$. Lemma 2 is relevant.

Lemma 2: Consider the nonlinear impulsive system (7) and Assumptions 1-3. Controller (8) guarantees the boundedness of $s(t)$, $V_s(t)$ and that $\xi \in (-1, 1)^{2p}$.

Proof: Let us define $\bar{B} := \max \{\bar{B}_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$. Hence we conclude from (18):

$$\dot{V} \leq -\frac{k_s \lambda_A \|\zeta\|^4}{6} + \frac{\bar{B}^2}{4k'_s \lambda_A}, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t_1].$$

Therefore, there exists a constant $l_1 > 0$ such that

$$\dot{V} \leq -l_1 \|\zeta\|^4, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t_1],$$

provided that $|\zeta| \geq \sqrt[4]{\frac{\bar{B}^2}{4k'_s \lambda_A (k_s \lambda_A / 6 - l_1)}}$. Defining $l' = 4l_1$ and utilizing the definition of V , we conclude that:

$$\dot{V} \leq -l' V^2, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t_1], \quad (24)$$

provided that $|\zeta| \geq \sqrt[4]{\frac{\bar{B}^2}{k'_s \lambda_A (4k_s \lambda_A / 6 - l')}}$. To continue, we distinguish two cases.

Case 1 ($|\zeta| \leq \sqrt[4]{\bar{B}^2 / (k'_s \lambda_A (4k_s \lambda_A / 6 - l'))}$): We proved that \dot{V} is negative when $|\zeta| > \sqrt[4]{\bar{B}^2 / (k'_s \lambda_A (4k_s \lambda_A / 6 - l'))}$. Therefore, $\sqrt[4]{\bar{B}^2 / (k'_s \lambda_A (4k_s \lambda_A / 6 - l'))}$ is the upper bound of $|\zeta|$ for all $t \in [t_0, t_1]$. As a result, $\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\bar{B}^2 / (k'_s \lambda_A (4k_s \lambda_A / 6 - l'))}$ is the upper bound of $V(t)$, for all $t \in [t_0, t_1]$.

Case 2 ($|\zeta| > \sqrt[4]{\bar{B}^2/(k'_s \lambda_A(4k_s \lambda_A/6 - l'))}$): By the continuity of ζ , there exists a time constant $t'_1 \leq t_1$ such that $|\zeta| > \sqrt[4]{\bar{B}^2/(k'_s \lambda_A(4k_s \lambda_A/6 - l'))}$, for all $t \in [t_0, t'_1]$. Therefore, integrating (24) yields

$$V(t) \leq \frac{V(t_0)}{l'V(t_0)(t-t_0)+1}, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t'_1].$$

If $t'_1 < t_1$ then the same arguments as in Case 1 apply for all $t \in [t'_1, t_1]$. Therefore, aggregating both cases we obtain that for all $t \in [t_0, t_1]$

$$V(t) \leq \max \left\{ \frac{V(t_0)}{l'V(t_0)(t-t_0)+1}, \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\bar{B}^2}{k'_s \lambda_A(4k_s \lambda_A/6 - l')}} \right\}. \quad (25)$$

Consequently, utilizing Assumption 2, we have

$$V(t_1^-) \leq \bar{V} = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{l'_1 \bar{\tau}}, \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\bar{B}^2}{k'_s \lambda_A(4k_s \lambda_A/6 - l')}} \right\}.$$

Define $E(k)$ the energy injected to $V(t)$ when $t \in \mathbb{J}$. Then owing to Assumption 3, $E(k)$ is bounded for all $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$. Hence, $V(t_1) = V(t_1^-) + E(1) \leq \bar{V} + E(1)$. Thus,

$$V(t) \leq \max \{V(t_0), \bar{V} + E(1)\}, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t_1].$$

Therefore by induction, we obtain for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $k \geq 2$

$$V(t_k) = V(t_k^-) + E(k) \leq \bar{V} + E(k),$$

$$V(t) \leq \max \{\bar{V} + E(k-1), \bar{V} + E(k)\}, \quad \forall t \in [t_{k-1}, t_k].$$

Aggregating over all time intervals, yields

$$V(t) \leq \max \{V(t_0), \bar{V} + E(1), \dots, \bar{V} + E(k)\}, \quad \forall t \geq t_0.$$

Hence, since \bar{V} and $V(t_0)$ are bounded independently of k and $E(k)$ is bounded, we obtain that $V(t)$ is bounded for all $t \in [t_0, \infty)$, which leads to the boundedness of $\zeta(t)$ and therefore to the boundedness of $\epsilon(t)$. From the latter, we straightforwardly conclude that $\xi(t) \in (-1, 1)^{2p}$, for all $t \geq t_0$.

V. SIMULATIONS

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed controller, we assume a free-flying pinhole camera with respect to a target in the 3D Cartesian space. Four feature points, forming a rectangle with edges 0.4cm and 0.3cm, formulate the target. The pinhole camera provides an image of 1280×720 pixels with focal length $f_c = 538$ pixels. Therefore, the field of view constraints are $\chi_M = -\chi_m = 640$ and $\psi_M = -\psi_m = 360$. The initial position of the camera, in the 3D Cartesian space, is $p_c = [0.67 \quad -0.52 \quad -0.52 \quad -42.5 \quad 45.4 \quad 90]$, where the first three arguments are the position as in $\{x_c \ y_c \ z_c\}$, while the rest are the rotation matrix expressed in Euler angles as $\{\alpha_c \ \beta_c \ \gamma_c\}$ and $R_c = Rot(x, \alpha_c)Rot(y, \beta_c)Rot(z, \gamma_c)$. The initial overall visual feature vector is $s_0 = [-136.75 \quad 13.81 \quad 15.35 \quad -76.14 \quad -22.21 \quad 110.16 \quad 129.49 \quad -13.08]$ (pixels). The desired overall visual feature vector is set to $s^* = [-215.2 \quad -161.4 \quad 215.2 \quad -161.4 \quad -215.2 \quad 161.4 \quad 215.2 \quad 161.4]$ (pixels). The features are

subject to impulsive perturbations every three seconds for the first nine seconds. Their values at the time of impulses are provided at Table I. It is desired, that each feature error converge not later than the fixed time $\tau = 2$ seconds to the interior of the set $\{e_i^\sigma \in \mathbb{R} : |e_i^\sigma(t)| \leq 30\}$ (pixels) for $i = 1, \dots, 4$ and $\sigma = \{\chi, \psi\}$. Therefore, we select $\delta_i = 30$. Notice, also, that $\tau < \bar{\tau} = 3$ seconds. To achieve smooth feature evolution with reasonable control effort, we select all other control elements according to Theorem 1 as $\bar{\beta}_i = \beta_i = 2$, $k_s = k'_s = 25$, $\rho_i^\infty = 3$ and $\lambda_{i,0} = 1.736$ for $i = 1, \dots, 4$. We choose the rest of the $\lambda_{i,j}$, $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ according to (8d). Furthermore, as stated in Remark 2, we set $\rho_{i,k}^\sigma = \underline{W}_i^\sigma$ and $\bar{\rho}_{i,k}^\sigma = \bar{W}_i^\sigma$, where $\underline{W}_1^\chi = \underline{W}_3^\chi = \bar{W}_2^\chi = \bar{W}_4^\chi = 424.8$ (pixels), $\underline{W}_2^\chi = \underline{W}_4^\chi = \bar{W}_1^\chi = \bar{W}_3^\chi = 855.2$ (pixels), $\underline{W}_1^\psi = \underline{W}_2^\psi = \bar{W}_3^\psi = \bar{W}_4^\psi = 198.6$ (pixels) and $\underline{W}_3^\psi = \underline{W}_4^\psi = \bar{W}_1^\psi = \bar{W}_2^\psi = 521.4$ (pixels).

We picture the results in Figs. 2-4. Specifically, in Fig 2, we plot the evolution of the feature values illustrating the achievement of the visual servoing task. It is clear that no visual constraint is violated and that all visual features are kept for all times inside the field-of-view. In Fig 3, we present the evolution of the feature errors e_i^σ . All errors evolve strictly within the performance bounds as Theorem 1 predicts. Additionally, in Fig 4, we picture the requested control effort, clearly showing it is reasonably bounded despite the presence of the impulses.

TABLE I
FEATURES VALUES AT IMPULSE TIMES

	feature 1	feature 2	feature 3	feature 4
$t \in [0, 3)$				
x	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
y	-0.200	0.200	-0.200	0.200
z	0.150	0.150	-0.150	-0.150
$t \in [3, 6)$				
x	-0.110	-0.005	-0.072	0.033
y	-0.265	0.121	-0.295	0.090
z	0.175	0.149	-0.121	-0.147
$t \in [6, 9)$				
x	-0.129	-0.049	-0.146	-0.066
y	-0.173	0.175	-0.307	0.041
z	0.241	0.061	-0.027	-0.206
$t \geq 9$				
x	-0.078	-0.103	-0.236	-0.260
y	-0.264	0.135	-0.290	0.108
z	0.160	0.134	-0.094	-0.120

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Fig. 2. Evolution of the four features from the camera perspective. The desired positions are denoted with squares while the starting position with crosses. The dot lines represent the impulsive phenomenon, connecting the position before the impulse and right after.

Fig. 3. Evolution of the feature errors $e_i^\sigma = [\sigma]_i - [\sigma]_i^*$ alongside with their corresponding performance bounds for $i = 1, \dots, 4$ and $\sigma = \{\chi, \psi\}$.

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Fig. 4. The requested control inputs $V_{s,j}$ for $j = 1, \dots, 6$.

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